

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review Article On The Artificial Intelligence [Ai] In Tumour Detection [Oncology]

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 07 Nov. 2024

Keywords:

Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), colorectal malignancies, Malignant tumours, Deep radiomics, Mass fundus photography screening, Atherosclerosis, magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS), diffusion-weighted MRI (DW-MRI), dynamic contrast-superior MRI (DCE-MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), Natural language processing (NLP), Diabetic retinopathy.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14052089

ABSTRACT

artificial intelligence (AI) has proven to be highly proficient in image processing, predictive analytics, and precision oncology of various slides. Artificial intelligence (AI) is used in tumour pathology to diagnose, subtype, grade, stage, and estimate prognosis for nearly all types of cancers. It also helps in identify various pathological characteristics, biomarkers, and genetic alterations. A neural network is a mathematical structure that is designed to resemble neurons in the brain. It works by fitting a set of output variables iteratively using simple equations applied to input variables. Software applications that utilize the deep convolutional neural network computational architecture are primarily referred to as "deep studying". The computer process of interpreting natural language using algorithms to produce a useful alteration of a record based on input from a document or, more frequently, the result of automatic speech recognition is known as natural language processing. AI incorporates information from both the clinical and technical domains, cooperation between industry and academia is crucial to enhancing AI as a treatment. Every imaging technology that is now available is used in modern ophthalmology, including mechanical, electrical, magnetic, acoustic, optical, and others. It will thus be the pioneer in implementing and fully enforcing cutting-edge technical developments, detecting various tumours and others pathological diseases. Development of AI helpful for reducing work load for detecting tumours and helpful for low income families for easy diagnosis and less cost for patients.

INTRODUCTION

The development of digital pathology and progression of state-of-the-art algorithms for

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

computer vision have led to increasing interest in the use of artificial intelligence (AI), especially deep learning (DL)-based AI, in tumor pathology. [1] Regarding artificial intelligence (AI), McCarthy et al. made reference to the computer science movement of the 1950s, which used machine-based techniques to predict and imitate human intellect in analogous situations. Compared to other disease management applications, image-based diagnostic domains such as pathology, radiology, ultrasonography, and the diagnosis of skin and eye illnesses are more likely to employ artificial intelligence. Because pathological diagnosis is so complex and carries so much weight, it presents a special obstacle for applying artificial intelligence to this field. Large-scale digital slide libraries such as The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) have made it possible for researchers to openly access comprehensively curated and annotated pathological picture databases with clinical outcomes and genetic information. Digital pathology and oncology using quantitative AI research. A neural network is a mathematical structure built to mimic brain neurons in which simple equations applied to input variables are iteratively fitted against an output variable or variables. [2] The term "deep studying" mostly describes software applications that make use of the deep convolutional neural network computational framework. Simple equations applied to input variables are iteratively loaded against an output variable or variables in a mathematical structure called a neural community, which is designed to resemble brain neurons. The gadget is referred to as a deep neural community and has the ability to explain non intuitive variability in the data when layers of these equations are layered next to each other and fed through intermediary nodes. Google is also focused on application-facing research: its artificial intelligence company Deep Mind collaborated with a global network of partners to

build a model for the diagnosis of breast cancer in nearly 91,000 women. The version performed better than any human reader, and the authors proved that their approach could significantly reduce workload. Paige, a pathology-focused firm, collaborated with the Pathology branch of Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center to create the first clinical-grade deep learning model for cancer versus non-cancer diagnosis using whole-slide histology images. The National Institutes of Health developed a phone application to identify malaria from blood smears by calculating the ratio of healthy cells to parasitic blood cells using a deep learning version.

Statistics:

Co-founder of Google Brain Andrew Ng stated that the main barrier in deep learning is data, not techniques. In order to obtain enough data for training their medical-grade models, Paige and Google had to collaborate with healthcare facilities. Academic institutions are the primary source of biomedical facts, making them excellent candidates for record collection. Researchers in oncology who wish to conduct system learning can access these records: radiology images, raw gene expression/sequencing data, and clinical records in electronic medical facts that are already virtual. The biggest challenge, which is not always trivial, is digitizing pathology complete-slide images. The Paige team required more than a year to produce almost 44,000 entire-slide photos. A personalized treatment plan that is entirely dependent on the identification of target able biomarkers is the hallmark of precision oncology. For example, compared to individuals with MSI-low condition, patients with colorectal malignancies who have high degrees of microsatellite instability (MSI-high) have been demonstrated to benefit from immunotherapy treatment. MSI reputation is a potential digital biomarker that can be determined with an extreme degree of accuracy from pathology complete-slide photos. However,

training a biomarker for MSI popularity differs significantly from training a biomarker for immunotherapy response.

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs):

Machine learning algorithms can help to improve the accuracy and efficiency of cancer diagnosis, selection of personalized therapies and prediction of long-term outcomes. ^[3] Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are a pair of interconnected layers of artificial intelligence algorithms that can classify facts with little pre-processing and learnable weights. Convolution is a mathematical process that describes how much one function overlaps with another when it is shifted over. In medical image processing, convolution's ability to extract capabilities from input statistics is its most valuable feature. Raw picture pixels on the input end are interpreted by CNN to provide output scores. Deep CNNs are CNNs that have multiple CNN layers stacked. Comparing Deep-CNNs to modern photo reconstruction algorithms, there are many benefits. Firstly, deep-CNNs can significantly reduce the effort of explicit elaboration on feature extraction since they can quickly identify capabilities from a training information set. Additionally, the neuron-crafted functions can outperform and compensate for the classic feature extraction methods' discriminative electricity. Secondly, the inherent structure of a neuronal community has unique interplay and hierarchy that deep-CNNs can collectively exploit. As a result, the function selection process is greatly broadened and simplified.

AI packages in pediatric oncology imaging:

Deep-CNNs have been used to identify and categorize a variety of non-neoplastic anomalies in children, including pneumonia on chest radiographs and behind-schedule bone age from radiographs. Malignant tumours can be identified using analogous concepts: CNNs are adept in distinguishing between normal and abnormal scans. Tumour lesions on unusual scans may be

automatically identified, divided up, and measured. Adult hepatic tumors and tumor-free liver parenchyma were automatically segmented and their volumes assessed using deep-CNN by Lingururu et al. Tumors have also been represented by deep-cNNs. Tu et al. and Chen et al., for instance, employed machine learning methods to distinguish between benign and malignant lung nodules on pet/CT and chest CT scans. Using 18F-sodium fluoride (NaF) pet/CT scans, Perk et al. developed a wholebody automated disease type device to distinguish between benign bone lesions, which are typically degenerative alterations, and bone metastases.

Image-based biomarkers are particularly attractive, because they can provide a comprehensive view of the entire extent of the tumor and can capture regional tumor heterogeneity. ^[4] Recently, new approaches to structural, functional, and metabolic imaging have been developed to identify minute changes in the cytoarchitecture, chemical makeup, and metabolic processes of tumors. Examples include magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS), diffusion-weighted MRI (DW-MRI), dynamic contrast-superior MRI (DCE-MRI), positron emission tomography (PET) with particular molecular targets, and others. The most well-liked of them is 18F-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography (18F-FDG puppy), an imaging technique sensitive to tumor metabolism. The PERCIST 1.0 standards have led to the introduction of a set of guidelines for medical reporting and quantitative photo evaluation based on 18F-FDG pet.

Deep radiomics:

radiomics, which enables the development of novel potential biomarkers by analyzing a wide range of imaging capabilities that may not be readily apparent to a radiologist. Each of these potential biomarkers then becomes a hypothesis that could be investigated in a clinical setting. This

discovery method is one of the capabilities of contemporary AI approaches to scientific photo analysis, and it can help supplement current human knowledge. The greatest shared benefit of deep learning for image analysis is the ability to classify entire images into one or more groups, mainly according to factors like whether or not the images still show disease. The term “deep learning” comes from Geoffrey Hinton, Emeritus Professor of the University of Toronto, who is now known as the “Godfather” of AI. [5] Samala et al. carried out an experiment to transfer an already trained version for mammography to detect mass shadows in tomosynthetic breast images, demonstrating the efficacy of switch mastering. Federated mastering, which Google introduced in 2017, is defined as cooperative device learning without centralized education data and updates standard models with distributed statistics; it is also referred to as allotted learning. Under certain medical imaging conditions, this era would be acceptable, but there are often restrictions on the exchange of patient data between institutions due to legal, ethical, and/or technological concerns. Three different CAD types are categorized entirely according to their functions. - CADE (identification). CADx stands for prognosis. CADt stands for "triage." CADE and CADx are utilized to identify diseases in photos and categorize lesions as benign or malignant.

Fundus photos

Mass fundus photography screening can be used to diagnose not just the most common eye illnesses, such as glaucoma, but also diabetic retinopathy, hypertensive retinopathy, and arteriosclerosis diploma determination. Google obtained approximately one 130,000 fundus images and examined them the utilization of deep gaining grasp of . Because of this, Google produced an intriguing article in 2016 with a detection sensitivity of almost 98%, which is comparable to

an ophthalmologist's; this paper attracted a great deal of attention when it was published.

Dermatology photos:

The prognosis for most skin and pore cancers using AI has likewise caught up to, if not beyond, that of medical professionals. In January 2017, a studies institution at Stanford university used AI to diagnose skin cancer , their take a look at, photos of approximately a 130,000 skin lesions were amassed from the net, and “skin cancer (cancer),” “benign tumour,” etc. were discovered via deep studying, and as an end result, AI changed into able to diagnose skin most cancers with accuracy equivalent to a dermatologist. Wu et al. used more than a million images collected from more than 200,000 exams to study a CNN-primarily based version for breast cancer screening exam classification. They found that their model is just as accurate as experienced radiologists.

Computer vision algorithms ingest high dimensional image data and synthesize (or ‘convolute’) it to produce numerical or symbolic representations of concepts that are embedded in the image. [6]

automatic speech recognition:

automated speech reputation consists of a range of approaches that enable the translation of spoken language. Speech-reputation algorithms take raw speech waves from human speech and process them to enable the popularity of basic speech characteristics like pitch, tempo, timbre, and quantity, as well as more complex speech functions like spoken language, phrases, and sentences. More sophisticated speech recognition algorithms are able to recognize cutting-edge characteristics from audiological data, such as emotional states or mood swings. Traditional speech-popularity algorithms have typically relied on distinct trends to piece together meaning from spoken language because of the temporal complexity of speech.

herbal language processing:

Natural language processing (NLP) is the computer process of deriving meaning from natural language using algorithms that take input from a document or, more likely, the output of automatic speech recognition, and produce a useful modification of the record. Translation into another language, file classification, summary, or the extraction of higher-level standards from the text are some examples of this variant. Normal natural language processing (NLP) algorithms include syntactic evaluation, which parses written textual content using various techniques to extract useful computational representations of language (e.g., breaking sentences, labeling speech components, standardizing inflected words bureaucracy). Semantic evaluation then extracts meaning and/or named entity identities from the text.

challenges and limitations:

The ability of AI-based algorithms to understand complex data may be superhuman. However, its intricacy and electricity can also lead to erroneous, sometimes immoral, and prejudiced findings when applied to data on human health. The usefulness of those structures in medical diagnostics is limited if the methods and biases built into a trained AI device are not carefully considered. radiology, multiple evaluations have demonstrated that AI tools can differentiate between high- and low-risk lesions on a wide variety of imaging modalities. [7] AI is prone to social prejudice as well; for example, disparities in healthcare delivery consistently result in less than ideal outcomes for specific companies. Black patients were not always excluded from the educational data set; rather, doctors have historically under treated pain in black patients due to unconscious biases. For instance, if an AI model had been developed to help with pain control, the resulting algorithm should potentially offer suboptimal predictions for black sufferers.

Oncology: Artificial intelligence (AI) in oncology

has demonstrated precise technical performance in image processing, predictive analytics, and precision oncology delivery. It may also be utilized in the future to help avoid primary malignancies. A vast multidisciplinary effort would be required to fund and conduct future studies, as well as to educate and train the body of workers in oncology, standardize statistics sets, study reporting, validation methodologies, and regulatory requirements. Thus, in the era of large facts in oncology, forming alliances across healthcare systems, academia, business, and public enterprises may be essential to AI deployment.

Sirinukunwattana et al. proposed a deep learning method based on spatially constrained convolutional neural network for detecting and classifying cell nuclei in colon cancer tissue. [8] Technological developments in artificial intelligence (AI) suggest that AI could revolutionize the way most tumours are investigated, diagnosed, and treated. Positive scientific results, such a patient's response to anti-cancer pills or combinations of such capsules, may be anticipated by AI in the near future. Through the analysis of large datasets, artificial intelligence (AI) may be used to identify new therapeutic targets for the majority of cancer types and cancer patients, as well as new cancer mechanisms and indicators of treatment response. For example, tumour cells can be scanned directly in tissue or after being grown and treated with pharmaceutical drugs. Deep-learning methods can then be used to evaluate the resulting images to uncover characteristics linked to drug reactivity or disease processes, such as metastasis.

Liquid Biopsy: Cohen et al. developed a blood test called Cancer SEEK, which employs discriminative learning to screen for eight distinct types of cancer and probably detect the proximity of tumours. It functions by combining proteins for genes linked to cancer and genetic variations for cancer-associated genes. Protein biomarkers are

then used to help localize the cancer (which may help detect tumours that originate in different locations but share similar oncogenic drivers). An average pan-most cancers sensitivity of 70% was attained by the researchers, with an ovarian most cancers sensitivity of 98%. Moreover, urine can easily be employed as a source of cloth for liquid biopsies, particularly in cases of genito-urinary tract cancer. for instance Urine can be utilized to identify the majority of bladder tumours, particularly as it may contain higher-quality DNA than plasma does.

The software of AI for anti-cancers drug discovery and improvement:

The process of improving drugs is expensive and time-consuming; it can cost up to \$2.8 billion and take up to 15 years. Drug development is a very failure-prone area of study, and extensive research has been done to improve the process using artificial intelligence. Since the process of creating and evaluating novel active compounds is expensive, time-consuming, and prone to error, deep generative models have become a viable option for more environmentally friendly chemical design. A neural community trained on extant chemical systems was used in one of the first studies to create a "molecular auto encoder" (Gomez-Bombarelli et al., 2016). The group converted discrete representations of molecules into continuous vector representations, enabling them to predict chemical homes from the latent vector representations of these molecules. They were able to carry out operations inside the latent area (decoding random vectors, disrupting chemical structures) to search for compounds that might act as novel anticancer agents by using those continuous representations. Diagnosing involves the exclusion of other benign disease processes and the characterization of cancer by primary site, histopathology, and, increasingly, genomic classification. ^[9] The field of oncology research, the burgeoning information era, and the

developments in computer technology have all contributed to a paradigm shift in patient statistics illustration from low-dimensional to progressively high-dimensional. Reduced unstructured patient statistics (e.g., clinical pictures and biopsies) into a set of human-digestible discrete indicators of illness extent was sometimes necessary due to previous records and computing constraints. A remarkable illustration of this kind of simplification may be seen in cancer staging systems, most notably the TNM category of the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) (Amin et al., 2017). In 1977, the first iteration of AJCC TNM staging was developed, and it used the three most prevalent inputs at the time—tumor size, nodal involvement, and evidence of metastasis (TNM)—to establish the standard for risk classification and decision-making in oncology.

Radiomics And Biomarkers:

Deep learning based radiomic (DLR) features are obtained by normalizing the information from deep neural networks, especially CNNs, designed for image segmentation. ^[10] Radiomics and biomarkers choice and quantification are strongly interdependent with advanced ML/DL algorithms, which have to be carefully used and extensively evaluated earlier than being deployed in scientific practice. There are nonetheless several boundaries and challenges to be addressed within the scientific software of AI in oncology, consisting of the explainability and interpretability of the models, the sensitivity of the functions' extraction, the reproducibility of the quantitative function choice and the harmonization of the data. radiomics has been brought as the high throughput extraction of "engineered" (or "hand made") capabilities from clinical pics . It has the potential to offer a quantitative signature of tumours' characteristics that can not be favored visually and has proven promising effects in identifying tumour subtypes and in predicting final results through

relying on ML strategies to exploit radiomic features in aggregate with scientific or other variables to construct predictive fashions. Category: The problem of class of clinical pix can be divided into two subproblems : image/exam category and item/lesion category. photograph classification considers an picture as a whole to are expecting a diagnostic output, e.g. presence of a positive sickness. Item type then again is involved with the category of predefined patches of an photo, e.g. whether a nodule is benign or cancerous. In picture category, mainly in scientific imaging, transfer learning is a totally famous method due to the comparatively small range of to be had pictures for a given task. From the arrival of automatic Tomography in the 1970 s, the quantity of scientific photograph records has been gradually increasing in the healthcare company. an ordinary CT within the 1970 s contained ~ 40 5-mm slices, while these days it could comprise greater than ~ 2 k 512 × 512 slices. The form of identity facts is found in numerous data, such as DICOM scientific images. There are several toolkits that dispose of this touchy facts like Conquest DICOM software , RSNA medical Trial Processor (CTP) , okay-p.c. , DICOM library , DICOMworks , PixelMed DICOMCleaner , DVTK DICOM anonymizer, YAKAMI DICOM equipment , and so forth. moreover, they could choose to convert information to a distinctive record layout together with NifTI (Neuroimaging Informatics generation Initiative) in order DICOM metadata. sensitive data is eliminated, leaving simplest the photo voxel size and affected person position for the AI set of rules. AI includes machine learning (ML), where an algorithm can selflearn through training without human intervention, as well as deep learning (DL), where artificial neural networks process and learn information using networks of much greater complexity. ^[11] There are actually greater than 64 FDA-cleared AI/ML-based clinical gadgets and

algorithms, lots of which are already integrated into clinical care , For most cancers care particularly, there are AI-powered algorithms to resource radiologists in reading CTs, mammograms, MRIs, bone density scans, echocardiograms, and lots of other styles of pics .more than one organizations, often counting on large collections of training pictures provided with the aid of NCI's cancer Imaging Archive, have advanced algorithms to examine chest CTs and mammograms, that allows you to enhance their predictive capacities. such tools aren't meant to replace educated experts, but they can be an important useful resource to specialists (e.g.shortening the time to read a given experiment) and they could provide an initial advice when a skilled expert isn't always at once on hand. It's additionally vital to note that such gear require careful medical evaluation and monitoring, even after FDA clearance, there are many thrilling examples of AI/ML tools for most cancers picture evaluation at numerous ranges of improvement. One is an AI-based totally method for the analysis of prostate cancer developed by means of NCI scientists. The algorithm analyzes MRI-guided biopsy snap shots of the prostate and is presently being utilized in clinics lacking trained prostate cancer specialists. another utility of AI comes from NCI researchers operating on an AI-focused cervical neoplasia screening test intended to be used in low resource regions . such a technology could be of particular fee in places like sub-Saharan Africa, where cervical most cancers mortality is very high, however where in get right of entry to clinics to cope with cervical neoplasia is restrained. This DL set of rules analyzes virtual snap shots of the cervix thinking about a mobile phone or different small digital camera, and then picks out precancerous modifications that require scientific interest. In facet-by-facet tests, the set of rules plays higher than human professionals reviewing conventional tests for cervical neoplasia

(e.g. the Pap smear). a chief gain of this method is that screening and treatment (if wished) can be finished in one visit, saving sufferers and fitness care people time, assets, and tour. AI/ML to expect protein folding, a long unsolved trouble in structural biology. higher prediction of protein folding could have extensive packages in primary cancer studies as well as drug improvement. Scientists at Deep Mind technology, a Google-owned AI agency within the united kingdom, have developed a DL algorithm known as Alpha Fold to expect how a protein will fold, primarily based totally on its amino acid series . Such data might be used by medicinal chemists to design better antibody-based totally pills to deal with cancer, or by using cancer immunologists to higher recognize an anti-tumour immune reaction by predicting epitope binding to T-mobile receptors. Deep learning has revolutionized image analysis since its spectacular win in the image recognition contest ILSVRC. ^[12] In developed nations, cancer is the most common cause of death, and as the population gets older, there will likely be an increase in the disease's incidence. Every year, around 400 000 people in Japan lose their lives to cancer, accounting for nearly 1 million new cases of the disease. Therefore, research on the majority of cancers will continue to be of utmost importance in terms of saving lives. Deep neural networks come in a variety of architectural forms. In order to identify patterns in the statistics, a convolutional neural network (CNN) applies many filters on data that has a grid structure, such as snapshots. A fully convolutional network (FCN), as contrast to a CNN, substitutes upsampling and deconvolution layers—which are essentially the opposite of the pooling and convolution layers, respectively—for each pertinent layer in the CNN (determine second). An FCN makes a rating map for every class rather than a single chance score. This map, which has the exact same size as the input image, uses pixels to categorize the image.

Several packages used these extra layers to expand on deep learning methods . Thus, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are useful for processing sequential data, like genetic sequences and language. Neural networks like these are linked to supervised learning techniques that require community training solutions. software for image analysis Early detection is crucial for the majority of cancers in order to preserve the lives of individuals who are affected. Collaboration between industry and academia is essential to improving AI as a treatment since it involves knowledge from both the clinical and technical realms. ^[13] However, because the technical and medical viewpoints do not always coincide, it is imperative that this kind of partnership be referred to as medical leading rather than technical leading. AI development, integration, and application are expensive, not only because the technology is still in its infancy and not yet a ready-to-use product, but also because it involves potential costs for scientific experts. Medical personnel are not providing treatment for patients or conducting more conventional types of research during the time they are training an AI system.

[AI] In Ophthalmology:

Diabetic retinopathy is the most common organ complication and can manifest as the earliest sign of complication of diabetes mellitus. ^[14] Currently, modern ophthalmology uses every imaging technology available, including mechanical, electrical, magnetic, acoustic, optical, and others. As a result, it will be the first to fully enforce and adopt new technological trends, such as artificial intelligence. Ophthalmologists should fully embrace the AI era and leverage it to market advancements in ocular pharmaceuticals as much as is practical. The applications of deep learning, specifically in retinal images, include classification (e.g., fundus pictures can be used to detect diabetic retinopathy (DR) and diabetic macular edema (DME); segmentation (e.g., brain,

lungs, and mobile mitosis); and prediction (e.g., myopia development and development can be predicted). Three ranges can be used to define the deep learning process: (1) Pre-processing of the picture statistics; (2) version, validation, and education [3] assessment, Power, STARE, photograph-Ret, e-optha, HEI-MED, Retinopathy online initiative, Messidor, RIM-ONE, and DRION-DB are among the frequently used fundus databases. The most often used among them to diagnose DR are Force, STARE, image-Ret, and Messidor; on the other hand, DRION-DB and RIM-ONE are mostly used to segment the optic nerve head in the context of diagnosing glaucoma. The most prevalent organ impairment is diabetic retinopathy, which might occur as the first indication of a diabetic mellitus consequence. It's critical to diagnose and monitor DR as soon as possible in order to treat the condition and prevent blindness. Many different types of attention have been drawn to the automated identification of DR. Fundus photos are used as an input in maximum automatic approaches.

CONCLUSION:

Human beings are suffering with different type of diseases and trauma ,disorders and by developing the artificial intelligence helps in diagnosis of different diseases . AI also reduces the cost of diagnosis and reduces the work stress for the pathologists. Building the AI for tumour detection we get accurate results and get the easy conclusion about the disease type of tumour ,diagnosis of the tumour. Machine learning algorithms and convoulutional neural networks and its upgrades with new diseases helps in easy diagnosis and type of tumour. Training the AI with various pathology photos and dermatology slides finding the type of disease or skin disease is easy. Oncology is the vast topic it takes years to get easy conclusion and treatment about 100 percent but training the AI we can overcome all the diagnostic problems with less less cost and its also helpful for the middle class

and low income families. AI ophthalmology helps in detecting the diabetic retinopathy and others corneal complications, diabetic macular edema and more.

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HOW TO CITE: Padala Ramesh*, Patnala Vaishnavi Gayathri, Mamindla Chandrika, Daravath Pawan Kalyan, A Review Article On The Artificial Intelligence [Ai] In Tumour Detection [Oncology], *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 11, 383-392. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14052089>